

Study on nucleation and crystallization kinetics of polypropylene using bisphenol-A disodium as nucleating agent

Harshad R. Patil^{a,b}, Parimal A. Parikh^a and Z. V. P. Murthy^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Sardar Vallabhbhai National Institute of Technology, Surat-395 007, Gujarat, India

E-mail : zvpm2000@yahoo.com, zvpm@ched.svnit.ac.in Fax : 91-261-2227334, 2228394

^bReliance Industries Limited, Hazira Manufacturing Division, Surat-394 510, Gujarat, India

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Abstract : Salt of bisphenol-A is explored for polypropylene nucleation and crystallization. Synthesized compound, sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA), showed nucleation efficiency as indicated by 2.6 and 6.4 °C improvement in crystallization temperature (0.4 and 1 wt% loading of SBPA, respectively) of polypropylene (PP) by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), lower spherulite size and increase of transmittance of PP film by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The nucleation performance results of SBPA were compared with PP nucleated by commercial nucleating agent, sodium benzoate (SB), which has single aromatic ring structure. Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) and crystallite study of PP nucleated by SBPA and SB revealed possible explanation for correlating structure of nucleating agent with PP nucleation and crystallization. The nucleation effect of SBPA for PP was further substantiated by non-isothermal crystallization study by modified Avrami approach and was compared with PP without nucleating agent. SBPA was evaluated through Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis for confirmation.

Keywords : Nucleating agent, crystallization, polypropylene, DSC, modified Avrami approach.

Introduction

The demand for polypropylene, very important and indispensable polymer, has been growing at an annual rate of 6% with world wide production of more than 30 million tons¹. Polypropylene (PP) production and processing industry became important due to PP applications in automobiles, home appliances, household items, packaging of foods, fertilizer, cements, virtually touching every sphere of human life. PP has become an important polymer due to its unique properties and higher strength-to-cost ratio as compared to other commodity polymers. Additives are added to PP for achieving desired characteristics of PP. One of the important class of additives used is nucleating agent, which has several advantages like improvement in production of injection molding articles due to increase in crystallization temperature, improvement in stiffness and providing dimensional stability to molded articles^{2,3}.

One of the compounds used for commercial applications is sodium benzoate (SB), which increases crystalli-

zation temperature and stiffness of PP^{4,5}. Presence of aromatic structure leads to insolubilization of nucleating agents in PP matrix and forms layers, one above another, for nucleation and crystallization⁶. The combination of aromatic ring and carboxylic group structure, as nucleating agent, has been widely studied. However, derivatives of phenolic groups, linked by alkyl group, bisphenol-A (BPA) type structures, have been explored to limited extent as nucleating agent. Study of new aromatic structures will help to understand new kind of nucleating agents, in addition to currently used commercial structures. BPA is also used in the production of polymers, like polyesters, polysulfones, polycarbonates, etc., and also as additives for polyvinyl chloride. We have synthesized sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA) by reaction of BPA with sodium hydroxide in aqueous media⁷. SBPA was studied for physico-chemical characteristics by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis and particle size distribution (PSD).

The extruded PP at different concentrations (0.2, 0.4 and 1 wt%) of SBPA and SB was examined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)⁸. Spherulite formation of PP was examined by polarized optical microscopy (POM) and film transparency was studied by UV-Visible spectroscopy. A correlation between structure of nucleating agent and PP nucleation-crystallization has been proposed. Further, non-isothermal crystallization behavior of PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA and non-nucleated PP were studied by modified Avrami approach to ascertain the findings.

Experimental

Materials :

Bisphenol-A ($C_{15}H_{16}O_2$, 99.0%, M.W. = 228.3 g/mol), sodium hydroxide and sodium benzoate ($C_6H_5CO_2Na$, 99.0%) were procured from M/s. Labort Private Limited, India. Polypropylene, without any additive, was collected from commercial plant for nucleation study. PP has xylene soluble content of 5–5.5 wt%, melt flow index of 3–3.5 g/10 min and weighted average molecular weight (M_w) of 3.5×10^5 .

Nucleating agent synthesis methodology :

A 4.8 g (0.12 mol) of caustic flakes and 13.7 g (0.06 mol) bisphenol-A were dissolved in 50 g demineralized water in a round bottom flask, with condenser, at 70 °C for 30 min. The solution became transparent in nature, which was cooled to ambient temperature (30 °C), where formation of needle shaped crystals were observed. The solid product was washed multiple times with water to remove excess caustic and dried under vacuum at 70 °C to get dry and free flowing powder. The powder was crushed by mortar to reduce the particles size of SBPA.

Characterization of nucleating agent :

FTIR analysis was performed for synthesized salt using Perkin-Elmer spectrum GX instrument. Bisphenol-A indicates bending vibration peaks at 1360–1380 and 1435–1445 cm^{-1} (>C–O–H) which was having less intensity for FTIR spectra of SBPA due to the formation of >C–O–Na salt^{9,10}. Further, new peaks were observed for SBPA at stretching vibration of ~ 3575 and $3600 cm^{-1}$ due to -ONa formation (FTIR spectrum is given in supplementary information).

Morphology (SEM, FEI make, 12.5 kV supply volt-

age) study of SBPA indicated packed and non-filamentous structure without any void and having rough surfaces. Particles shape was irregular. EDX analysis (Oxford Instrument, INCA) exhibited uniform distribution of sodium on the surface of the particles. It also revealed 14.2 wt% Na (theoretical = 16.9 wt%) and 59.8 wt% C (theoretical = 66.2 wt%), which were closer to the theoretical values, indicating conversion of BPA to SBPA (SEM and EDX data are given in supplementary information). Particle size study (CILAS, 1180) of SBPA indicated broad particle size distribution with D_{10} of 15 μm (10% of particles are less than 15 μm), D_{50} of 68 μm and D_{90} of 322 μm . Mean particle size of SBPA was found to be 117 μm (PSD histogram is given in supplementary information).

Mixing of synthesized nucleating agent with polypropylene :

Sodium salt of bisphenol-A was mixed in homogenizer for 10 min with additive free PP. The resultant mixture was melt blended by laboratory extruder (M/s. Dynesco, USA) at 230 °C and then the extruded PP was used for nucleation study.

Characterization of nucleated polypropylene :

Crystallization of PP, nucleated by the synthesized nucleating agent, was studied using Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 temperature modulated system. Prior to sample study, the heat flow and temperature were calibrated with pure indium and standard empty aluminum pan was used for base line calibration under nitrogen atmosphere. PP sample of 5 to 7 mg was scanned from 60 to 230 °C at heating or cooling rate of 10 °C/min. Samples were subjected to two heating and cooling cycles and data of crystallization temperature (T_c) were recorded for the second cooling cycle.

Polypropylene film (nucleated by SBPA and non-nucleated) having 250 μm thickness was prepared by holding PP in compression molding machine at 230 °C for 10 min and then quenching up to 10 °C. UV-Visible spectrophotometer (PE Lambda35) was used to evaluate the transmittance of PP film at 800, 600 and 400 nm. WAXD measurements of PP were carried out using Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer. The step size of WAXD measurements was 0.02° from 5° to 70° and time per step was 12 s. Analysis of WAXD data was performed

using TOPASv 3.0 software supplied by Bruker AXS. Spherulite formation during crystallization was studied by Polarized Light Microscope Leica DM 2500P (USA) fitted with Hotstage Linkam THMS 600. The nucleated and non-nucleated PP samples were placed separately on a heating plate and sandwiched between a glass slide and a cover slip, and were heated to 230 °C at 20 °C/min, held at 230 °C for 5 min to destroy any trace of crystallinity, cooled to 128 °C at 5 °C/min and held at 128 °C for isothermal crystallization study. Images were captured at 100X magnification at every 30 s.

Results and discussion

Performance evaluation of synthesized compound for polypropylene nucleation :

Synthesized nucleating agent was mixed with additive free PP. A 0.2 wt% Untranox626 and Cynox2246 (antioxidants) were also added for stabilization during heating. SBPA (0.2, 0.4 and 1 wt%) was extruded at 230 °C as mentioned in the Experimental Section. PP without addition of nucleating agent (adding only antioxidants) was also extruded for comparison. Nucleated and non-nucleated PP samples were evaluated by DSC for determining nucleation effect.

Table 1 provides DSC results of PP nucleated by 0.2, 0.4 and 1 wt% SBPA. There was no substantial increase in peak crystallization temperature at 0.2 wt% SBPA. However, T_c increased substantially at 0.4 wt% and 1

Table 1. DSC data of polypropylene without nucleating agent and polypropylene (PP) with sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA) and sodium benzoate (SB)

Polypropylene with ^a	[#] T_{c_a} (°C)	[#] T_{c_b} (°C)	[#] T_{c_p} (°C)	[#] ΔH_c (J/g)	Crystallinity ^b (%)
Nil	113.7	104.3	109.5	81.9	46.3
0.2 wt% SBPA	115.0	105.1	109.9	82.3	46.5
0.4 wt% SBPA	119.0	106.7	112.1	87.7	49.5
1.0 wt% SBPA	122.1	110.1	115.9	88.6	50.0
0.2 wt% SB	126.3	116.9	121.5	90.0	50.8

^a0.2 wt % of Uitanox 626/Cyanox 2246 (1 : 1 by wt) in all samples;

[#] T_{c_a} = start of crystallization peak; T_{c_b} = end of crystallization peak; T_{c_p} = peak crystallization temperature; ΔH_c = enthalpy of crystallization; heating and cooling rate = 10 °C/min;

^bEnthalpy of crystallization for crystallinity calculation = 177 J/g.

wt% concentrations showing increase of 2.6 and 6.4 °C, respectively. Start and end of crystallization peak temperatures at 0.4 and 1 wt% SBPA shifted towards higher temperature.

Table 2 shows improvement in transmittance of PP film nucleated by SBPA at loading of 0.4 wt% and 1 wt% as compared to 0.2 wt%. This methodology has been used by Shihui and Yonghua¹¹. These findings substantiated the results of DSC, which showed that SBPA has better nucleation capability at 0.4 and 1 wt% loadings.

Table 2. Percent transmittance of polypropylene (PP) film without nucleating agent and with sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA) and sodium benzoate (SB)

Sample	400 nm	600 nm	800 nm
PP without nucleating agent	29.0	48.2	60.1
PP with 0.2 wt% SBPA	35.3	48.0	60.4
PP with 0.4 wt% SBPA	49.0	62.0	70.6
PP with 1.0 wt% SBPA	47.1	60.1	73.2
PP with 0.2 wt% SB	55.0	69.3	76.4

SBPA nucleated PP exhibited α -form of crystalline PP. This was revealed by strong WAXD peaks located at 2θ of 14.1, 16.9 and 18.5° corresponding to (110), (040) and (130) planes¹², respectively (Fig. 1). Crystallinity study from DSC indicated higher crystallinity for PP nucleated by SBPA (0.4 and 1% loadings) as compared to PP without nucleation. PP nucleated with commercial nucleating agent (SB) showed higher crystallinity as compared to SBPA (Table 1).

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffractograms of : (A) polypropylene without nucleating agent; (B) 0.4 wt% sodium salt of bisphenol-A and (C) 0.2 wt% sodium benzoate.

Crystallite size (D) vertical to lattice plane (hkl) could be obtained according to Scherrer equation¹³ :

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where k was factor for the crystal figure (in the present case $k = 0.89$). The λ was the wavelength of X-ray ($\lambda = 1.541 \text{ \AA}$, taking $\text{\AA} = 0.1 \text{ nm}$), and θ was the diffraction angle. The β was equal to $(B^2 - b_0^2)^{1/2}$, where B was width at half-tallness of the diffraction peak and b_0 was the broadening factor of the instrument. The calculation was done using (110) plane having highest intensity WAXD peak by TOPASv 3.0 software supplied by Bruker. The crystallite size of PP nucleated by SBPA was 86 \AA , which was lower than the crystallite size of PP without nucleating agent (113 \AA). PP with commercial nucleating agent (SB) exhibited crystallite size of 59 \AA (Table 3). The nucleation effect can be linked with structure of nucleating agent. Probably sodium benzoate provides higher

Table 3. Crystal parameter of polypropylene (PP) without nucleating agent and PP with sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA) and sodium benzoate (SB)

Sample	hkl^a	$2\theta^a$	$d_{hkl} (\text{\AA})^a$	$D (\text{\AA})^a$
PP without nucleating agent	110	14.0	6.23	113
PP with 0.4 wt% SBPA	110	14.1	6.29	86
PP with 0.2 wt% SB	110	13.9	6.20	59

^a hkl = plane; 2θ = peak position in WAXD spectra; $d_{hkl} (\text{\AA})$ = spacing between planes; $D (\text{\AA})$ = crystallite size.

nucleation density and also optimum steric control giving straight confirmation to larger numbers of PP chain (high crystallinity) as compared to SBPA. SBPA, being bulky in nature, exhibits less nucleation density giving relatively lower nucleation (less crystallinity).

We have tried to understand the transparency of PP film by correlating it with crystallite size of nucleated and non-nucleated PP. Crystallite is basic constituent of lamella which leads to formation of spherulite. Size of spherulite can have influence on transparency of film. Crystallite size of film without nucleating agent was the highest which might have led to larger size of spherulite, which had resulted in lower percentage transmittance of PP film (Table 2). Crystallite-to-spherulite size of film nucleated with SBPA might have been lower as compared to PP without nucleating agent leading to higher

transmittance of film. It was substantiated by polarized optimal microscopy image, during isothermal crystallization, which indicated that crystallization completed in 8 min for SBPA nucleated PP, while non-nucleated PP required 50 min. Spherulite size of SBPA nucleated PP is visibly smaller than non-nucleated PP (Fig. 2). Further, commercial nucleating agent might have resulted in lowest spherulite, among all, exhibiting highest transparency of film. The explanation has been given pictorially in Scheme 1, which indicates that steric properties of organic moieties associated with metal in nucleating agent influences nucleation and crystallization of PP.

Study of crystallization kinetics :

Out of the three concentrations of SBPA (0.2, 0.4 and 1 wt%) studied for PP nucleation, 0.4 wt% SBPA was further evaluated by non-isothermal crystallization kinetics using modified Avrami approach. Table 4 shows DSC data of PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA at various cooling rates (10, 20, 30 °C/min). Peak crystallization temperature values were higher for the PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA than that of non-nucleated PP at different cooling rates. It was also observed that crystallization starts at comparatively higher temperature for PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA as compared to PP without nucleating agent. Relative crystallinity (θ) can be defined with respect to temperature, as given below^{14,15} :

$$\theta = \frac{1}{\Delta Hc} \int_{T_0}^T \frac{dHc}{dT} dT \quad (2)$$

where, ΔHc represents total enthalpy of crystallization for a given cooling rate, dHc represents infinitesimal change in the enthalpy with infinitesimal change in temperature (dT), The T_0 and T represent the starting and arbitrary temperatures, respectively. Partial integration of crystallization peak of DSC at various temperatures provides θ at different temperatures. As per various cooling rates, the temperature parameter can be converted to time scale as :

$$t = \frac{T_0 - T}{\phi} \quad (3)$$

where, ϕ is the cooling rate of DSC. Temperature scale of X-axis in Figs. 3a₁ and 3b₁ can be converted to time scale using eq. (3). Figs. 3a₂ and 3b₂ indicate plots of θ vs t for PP without nucleating agent and PP with 0.4 wt%

Fig. 2A, 10 min

Fig. 2A, 20 min

Fig. 2A, 50 min

Fig. 2B, 3 min

Fig. 2B, 4 min

Fig. 2B, 8 min

Fig. 2. Polarized optical microscope image at 100X during isothermal crystallization for (A) non-nucleated polypropylene; (B) sodium salt of bisphenol-A nucleated polypropylene.

SBPA, respectively. These spectra provide useful information about start and end of crystallization process with respect to time at various cooling rates (10, 20 and 30 °C/min). One of the interesting observations was change of relative crystallinity pattern (curve nature in Figs. 3a₂ and 3b₂) on decreasing or increasing cooling rates. The curve became more inclined (slope decreased) at lower cooling rate, i.e. it requires more time to complete total crystallization process. The curve became steeper (slope increased relatively) in case of PP nucleated by SBPA,

indicating lowering in total crystallization time at comparable cooling rate. Crystallization half-time ($t_{1/2}$) indicates the time required to achieve 50% crystallinity and represents the rate of crystallization. The reciprocal of crystallization half-time ($1/t_{1/2}$) can be used for comparison of different nucleating agents¹⁶, which was obtained from relative crystallinity-time curves (Figs. 3a₂ and 3b₂). PP with 0.4 wt% SBPA showed higher value for reciprocal of crystallization half-time ($1/t_{1/2}$) as compared to PP without nucleating agent.

Fig. 3a₁

Fig. 3a₂

Fig. 3b₁

Fig. 3b₂

Fig. 3. Plots of relative crystallinity (θ) vs temperature (T) and relative crystallinity (θ) vs time (t) for non-isothermal crystallization of : (a) polypropylene without nucleating agent; (b) polypropylene nucleated by 0.4 wt% sodium salt of bisphenol-A.

Scheme 1. Pictorial representation of probable effect of nucleating agent structure on polypropylene crystallization.

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Fig. 4. Avrami plots for : (a) polypropylene without nucleating agent; (b) polypropylene nucleated by 0.4 wt% sodium salt of bisphenol-A.

In general, the common approach that is adopted to analyze non-isothermal crystallization kinetics is through modified Avrami equation^{14,15}, given as

$$1 - \theta = \exp(-k_t t^n) \quad (4)$$

Table 4. DSC data of polypropylene (PP) without nucleating agent and polypropylene nucleated by 0.4 wt% sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA) at various cooling rates

Cooling rate	PP without nucleating agent [#]				PP with 0.4 wt% SBPA [#]			
	T_{c_a} (°C)	T_{c_b} (°C)	T_{c_p} (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)	T_{c_a} (°C)	T_{c_b} (°C)	T_{c_p} (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)
10	113.7	104.3	109.5	81.9	119.0	106.7	112.1	87.7
20	113.3	95.5	104.3	81.7	113.9	99.9	105.9	82.2
30	109.7	88.7	99.9	78.8	109.8	94.5	101.5	81.4

[#] T_{c_a} = Start of crystallization peak; T_{c_b} = end of crystallization peak;
 T_{c_p} = peak crystallization temperature; ΔH_c = enthalpy of crystallization.

Table 5. Modified Avrami kinetics constant for polypropylene (PP) without nucleating agent and PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% sodium salt of bisphenol-A (SBPA)

Cooling rate	PP without nucleating agent [#]				PP with 0.4 wt% SBPA [#]			
	n	k_t (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	$1/t_{1/2}$ (min ⁻¹)	n	k_t (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	$1/t_{1/2}$ (min ⁻¹)
10	2.9	0.9	0.98	1.02	2.5	1.6	0.75	1.33
20	3.2	3.7	0.50	2.00	2.7	5.5	0.45	2.22
30	3.4	9.2	0.42	2.38	3.3	13.9	0.32	3.12

[#] n = Avrami exponent; k_t = crystallization rate constant; $t_{1/2}$ = crystallization half-time;
 $1/t_{1/2}$ = reciprocal of crystallization half-time.

here k_t represents crystallization rate constant, n depicts the Avrami exponent (defines type of nucleation and crystallization growth) and t represents time required to complete the crystallization process. Eq. (4) can be alternately written as :

$$\ln [-\ln (1 - \theta)] = \ln (kt) + n \ln (t) \quad (5)$$

Parameters k_t and n can be obtained by plotting $\ln [-\ln (1 - \theta)]$ vs $\ln (t)$ for eq. (5), as shown in Fig. 4, and the crystallization kinetics parameters are given in Table 5. It can be seen from Table 5 that the value of n (Avrami exponent) was in the range of 2.9–3.4 for PP without nucleating agent and 2.5–3.3 for PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA. These values indicated random nucleation and spherulitic growth for SBPA nucleated PP¹⁷. Value of k_t was higher for PP nucleated by 0.4 wt% SBPA as compared to PP without nucleating agent at cooling rate of 10, 20 and 30 °C/min.

Conclusions :

Sodium salt of bisphenol-A showed nucleation efficiency by improvement of crystallization temperature of PP at 0.4 and 1 wt% loadings. SBPA characterization by FTIR and EDX confirmed formation of sodium salt. SEM and PSD analysis indicated irregular shapes and broad particle size characteristics. SBPA nucleated PP has lower

spherulite size as compared to non-nucleated PP, validating findings of film transparency study by UV-Visible spectroscopy. Stericity of organic moieties, associated with metal, has shown influence on PP nucleation and crystallization as understood by DSC data of SB and SBPA nucleated PP. Non-isothermal crystallization using SBPA as nucleating agent revealed increase in crystallization rate constant and reciprocal of half-time for crystallization indicating random nucleation and spherulitic growth.

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